

pH-responsive Nanosystems for Targeted Drug Delivery to Glioblastoma Multiforme and MRI-facilitated Monitoring of Content Release

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Abstract

Despite the current state-of-the-art glioblastoma treatment options, a clear indication of therapeutic delivery and efficacy is still missing, especially in early therapy. Substantial advancements, particularly in the areas of image-guided and targeted therapy of the most aggressive type of brain cancer-Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM), are needed to improve the quality of life and survival rates of patients. Herein we describe a proof of principle study toward developing a novel methodology for non-invasive monitoring of the release of cargo molecules from theranostic nanoparticles. This is achieved by quantifying changes in longitudinal relaxation time (T_1) before and after the pH-responsive release of contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), from the pores of GBM-targeted mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs). The pores of MSNs were loaded either with the anticancer drug paclitaxel (PTX) or FDA-approved contrast agent Gadobutrol, and their retention inside the pores was ensured by covalent attachment of β -cyclodextrin monoaldehyde to hydrazine-functionalized MSN, through acidification-cleavable hydrazone linkage. *In vitro* studies using a GBM cell line revealed that the developed nanoparticles effectively delivered their therapeutic cargo, leading to cell death, which was further enhanced with additional functionalization of MSNs with glioma-homing oligopeptide chlorotoxin (CHX). Furthermore, the changes in T_1 , occurring in response to the release of GdB from the pores of MSNs were successfully demonstrated by MRI measurements. These results are promising for the development of MRI-based methodology for monitoring and tracking the release of therapeutic content in tumor tissues. It is envisioned that this approach using contrast agent-loaded nanoparticles, before the treatment with the drug-filled analogues, could be applied in the future to provide increasingly personalized clinical management of cancer patients.

INTRODUCTION

Regardless of recent advances in the field, the major limitations of the current cancer therapies generally include: 1) non-specific distribution of the antitumor agent, 2) poor delivery at adequate concentrations, 3) development of adverse effects due to a lack of specificity and the need to use high doses, 4) development of drug resistance. The application of nanotechnology in medicine offers new opportunities for overcoming the drawbacks of conventional cancer therapy and for developing new optimized diagnostic tools. An increasing number of novel nanoparticulate delivery systems are being developed that contain different combinations of therapeutic and diagnostic (theranostic) agents on the same nanoparticle (NP), allowing real-time tracking of the therapy progress.^{1,2} The diagnosis of cancer using this approach is typically performed by enabling a selective imaging of the cancer tissue, using agents such as radioluminescent materials,³ cyanine-based fluorescent dyes,⁴ near infra-red (NIR) fluorophores,⁵ radionuclides,⁶ or magnetic resonance imaging contrast agents (MRI-CA),⁷ attached to the drug-containing nanoparticles.

The major advantages of MRI over other imaging modalities include non-invasiveness, no use of ionizing radiation, extremely clear and detailed images of soft structures, deep tissue imaging and relatively rapid

scanning.

Stimuli-responsive drug delivery systems (DDSs) show a great potential for the safely delivering drugs to specific target areas while avoiding the adverse effects of cytotoxic drugs.^{8,9} However, even in the case of nanomedicines containing cancer-targeting modalities (e.g. presence of tumor-specific ligands with stimuli-responsive triggering of drug release), the cancer-targeted therapy may still not be successful on all patients.¹⁰ This may be due to the irregular and unpredictable vasculature and morphology of cancerous tissue¹¹ or to non-release of the cargo. In fact, the presence of nanoparticles at the site of disease does not mean that the therapeutics are released and active against the tumour.

In this work, we describe for the first time a novel MRI-based methodology concept that could allow real-time monitoring of cargo release from nanocarriers at the site of disease. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) are suitable scaffolds for the construction of such nanotheranostics.¹² They exhibit sturdy and predictable structures, which are not affected by the molecules loaded within their mesopores. MSNs characteristics in terms of morphology, biodistribution, and interactions with biomolecules and tissues, are not expected to change significantly by replacing the CA cargo by drugs, ensuring the same, or highly similar, cancer-targeting ability or responsiveness to triggering stimuli, which might eventually enable clinicians to estimate the effectiveness of the drug-filled nanomedicines. Further benefits of MSNs include their facile surface functionalization, high surface area, high porosity, and particle diameter in a suitable range to exploit the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect in cancerous tissues.¹³ In addition, the drug-carrying MSNs can be functionalized with cancer-homing ligands and designed to release the therapeutic cargo molecules upon exposure to specific stimuli, such as intratumoral molecules, pH changes or external stimuli (e.g., light or a magnetic field).¹⁴ Under these circumstances, a minor release of the capped molecules is typically noted prior to exposure to the stimuli but larger amounts are released subsequently.

In vivo studies have already demonstrated the biocompatibility of MSNs and their capabilities to accumulate in tumors and effectively deliver anticancer drugs.^{15,16} When coating with a poly(ethylene glycol)-poly(ethylene imine) (PEG-PEI) block copolymer layer, the uptake of MSNs across the blood brain barrier (BBB) was also noted.¹⁷ Recent studies by our team in this research area have demonstrated the use of MSNs for local treatment of GBM.¹⁸⁻²⁰

In the current research study, the pores of MSNs were loaded either with the anticancer drug paclitaxel (PTX) or with the MRI-CA gadobutrol (GdB), and entrapped by pore-blocking with β -cyclodextrin (CD) moieties, which were covalently attached to MSN through acidification-cleavable hydrazone linkage (Scheme 1a,b).²¹ Cyclodextrins are typically used in the pharmaceutical industry as complexing agents to increase the aqueous solubility of poorly soluble drugs.²² Hence, the use of CDs may be helpful for improving the solubilization of the poorly soluble PTX if jointly released from the NPs, though its primary function in our NP assembly was as gatekeepers.^{23,24} Further functionalization of the nanoparticles (Scheme 1c) was conducted with oligopeptide Chlorotoxin (CHX), a small neurotoxin of 36 amino acids

which was shown penetrating the BBB,²⁵ and holding great promise for the treatment of glioma and other solid tumors.²⁶ Functionalization of CHX on the surface of magnetic NPs was also shown to enhance the treatment capabilities on rat C6 glioma cells.²⁷ Matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP-2) is expressed at higher level in gliomas than in normal brain tissues,²⁸ and CHX has previously been reported to be an efficient targeting ligand for this gelatinase.^{29,30} Therefore, it is postulated that CHX functionalization would enable an efficient targeting of brain tumors.

The newly developed materials were physico-chemically characterized by different methods such as SEM, TEM, XRD, nitrogen sorption porosimetry, DLS, zeta potential, TGA, DSC and FTIR spectroscopy. The pH-responsive release kinetics of GdB was monitored by fluorescence spectroscopy while the release of PTX was determined by UV/VIS spectroscopy. *In vitro* studies, including confocal microscopy, flow cytometry and toxicity measurements were performed on the human U87 GBM cell line. Finally, the changes in MRI relaxation occurring in response to the release of GdB were measured from the buffered suspensions of GdB-loaded material at pH 5.0 and 7.4.

METHODS

Materials

All reagents and solvents were purchased and used as received. Paclitaxel (PTX) was purchased from Alfa Aesar, while tetraethoxysilane (TEOS), aminopropyltrimethoxysilane (APTMS), mercaptopropyl trimethoxysilane (MPTMS), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), β -cyclodextrin (CD), Dess Martin periodinane (DMP), adamantylamine (AA), N- β -maleimidopropionic acid hydrazide (BMPH), gadobutrol monohydrate (GdB), glutaraldehyde (GA), chlorotoxin (CHX), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and dichloromethane (DCM), were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Minimum Essential Medium Eagle (MEM), L-glutamine, fetal bovine serum (FBS) and Hoechst 33342 were purchased from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). The ActinRed™ 555 ReadyProbes™ Reagent by Invitrogen was provided by Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA), while the Cell Proliferation/Cytotoxicity Assay CCK-8 by Dojindo EU GmbH (Munich, Germany).

Synthesis of mercaptopropyl-functionalized MSN material (MPMSN)

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, 1 g, 2.74 mmol) was first dissolved in 480 mL of water. NaOH (aq) (2 M, 3.50 mL) was added to the CTAB solution, followed by adjusting the solution temperature to 80°C. Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, 5 mL, 25.7 mmol) was first introduced dropwise to the surfactant solution, followed by dropwise addition of (3-mercaptopropyl) trimethoxysilane (MPTMS, 0.97 mL, 5.13 mmol). The mixture was allowed to stir for 2 h to give rise to a white precipitate (as-synthesized MPMSN). The solid product was filtered, washed with copious amounts of deionized water and ethanol, and dried at 80°C to stabilize the mesoporous structure. Final mercaptopropyl-MSN material (MPMSN) was obtained upon removal of the CTAB surfactant template by extraction with a solution of

concentrated HCl in methanol (1%, v/v). After 6 h of extraction, the material was additionally washed with deionized water and ethanol, and again dried at 80°C.

Synthesis of BMPH-MPMSN

120 mg of BMPH was dissolved in 40 mL of water followed by the addition of 800 mg of MPMSN. The mixture was stirred for 24h at room temperature. The material was then isolated via centrifugation, washed three times with water, once with ethanol and dried at 80°C.

Oxidation of β -cyclodextrin to CD-CHO

The procedure for oxidation of β -CD was done as previously published.^{31,32} Namely, 0.20 g of β -CD were dissolved in 5 mL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), 2 equiv. of Dess Martin periodinane (DMP) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. Addition of 150 mL of acetone and cooling allowed the isolation of the crude product CD monoaldehyde by filtration.

Synthesis of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN

GdB (4 mg) was dissolved in 1 mL of PBS (10 mM, pH 7.4). BMPH-MPMSN (30 mg) was added and stirred for 24 h at room temperature in dark. Then, 30 mg of β -CD-CHO was added, and the stirring continued for another 24 h. Finally, 2 mg of GdB and 0.3 mmol of adamantylamine (57 mg) were stirred for 1h in 0.5 mL PBS and added to the MSN-containing suspension. Stirring continued for another 6 h and the mixture was then centrifuged for 10 min at 11000 rpm and washed three times with PBS. All supernatants were saved and used for the calculation of the GdB loading. The material was dried at 80°C.

Synthesis of CHX-GdB@BMPH-MPMSN

The first part of the loading protocol was the same as described above for GdB@BMPH-MPMSN, and after the final washes with PBS, the materials were further functionalized with CHX as follows: PBS solution (1 mL) containing 0.3 mmol of glutaraldehyde was added to the GdB@BMPH-MPMSN material and stirred at room temperature for 2 h, followed by washing three times with 15 mL of PBS. After the final centrifugation, the material was redispersed in 0.7 mL of PBS and 0.3 mL of CHX (12 μ g) aqueous solution was added. The mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature in the dark, washed three times with PBS and dried in air. All supernatants were saved and used for the calculation of the GdB loading.

Synthesis of PTX@BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN

PTX (14.07 mg) was dissolved in 3 mL of dichloromethane (DCM). Then, 150 mg of BMPH-MPMSN was added and the mixture was allowed to stir for 24 h at room temperature in the dark. The DCM was evaporated under vacuum at room temperature. Then, 3 mL of PBS solution (10 mM, pH 7.4) containing 150 mg of β -CD-CHO was added and stirred for another 20 h at room temperature in the dark. The reaction mixture was divided into two fractions and one half was centrifuged, washed three times with 15

mL of PBS and twice with 2 mL of acetonitrile. Finally, the obtained PTX@BMPH-MPMSN material was dried in air.

The second fraction was further modified with glutaraldehyde-adamantylamine (GA-AA) conjugate, which was first prepared by mixing 0.03 mmol GA and 0.03 mmol AA in PBS solution (1 mg/mL). After addition of GA-AA, the stirring continued for 6 h under the same conditions. The material was then centrifuged, washed twice with PBS and redispersed in 1 mL of water containing 250 μ L of CHX solution (40 μ g/mL). The stirring continued for 24 h in the dark at room temperature and the as-synthesized CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN material was isolated by centrifugation, washed with PBS and dried in air.

Synthesis of FITC-labeled materials

Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC, 1 mg, 2.6 μ mol) was added to 3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane (APTMS) (2.6 μ mol) in dry DMSO (0.5 mL), stirred for 30 min and then added to a suspension of BMPH-MPMSNs (25 mg) in 10 mL of dry toluene. The suspension was refluxed for 6 h at 110°C, under nitrogen. After cooling, the resulting material was centrifuged, washed with toluene and ethanol. The obtained FITC-BMPH-MPMSN material was centrifuged and dried at 80 °C.

Solution of CD-CHO (20 mg) in 2 mL of PBS was added to 20 mg of FITC-BMPH-MPMSN and stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The mixture was centrifuged for 10 min at 11000 rpm, the supernatant decanted and a solution of adamantylamine hydrochloride (0.06 mmol, 11.4 mg) in 1 mL of phosphate buffer (0.1 M) was added to the precipitate. After stirring at room temperature for 16 h and washing with PBS, the material was resuspended in 10 mL of PBS and divided into two equal fractions. One of the fractions was centrifuged and dried at 80°C to yield AA-CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN material. The second sample was centrifuged and a solution of 0.1 mmol of glutaraldehyde dissolved in 1 mL of PBS was added to the material. The mixture was allowed to stir at room temperature for 2 h and then washed three times with PBS. The material was then redispersed in 1 mL of PBS and 0.1 mL of CHX (4 μ g) aqueous solution was added. The stirring continued for 24 h at room temperature in the dark, the material was washed three times with PBS and dried in air to yield CHX-AA-CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN.

Quantification of the loaded GdB contrast agent

The amounts of loaded GdB were measured by fluorescence spectroscopy ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 274$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 312$ nm), based on the prepared standard curves (Figure S1). The sum of the calculated amounts of GdB in the supernatants after all washings was subtracted from the initial amount of GdB which was added to the materials, to yield the loaded GdB. The formulae used to calculate the GdB concentration based on the standard curves are: $I = 95.514c + 269.2$ (pH 5), $I = 143.63c + 256.95$ (pH 6) and $I = 80.292c + 590.94$ (pH 7.4), where I is the intensity of the fluorescence at 312 nm, after excitation at 274 nm.

Quantification of the loaded PTX anticancer drug

The amount of loaded PTX was calculated by UV/VIS spectroscopy, by measuring the absorbance values at 230 nm from the mixtures of methanol (65.8%) and aqueous solutions, by adjusting a published procedure.³³ Calibration curves of PTX were obtained in solvent mixtures containing 65.8% of methanol and 34.2% of the following: acetate buffer at pH 5, PBS at pH 6 or pH 7.4, or water (Figure S2) Acetonitrile supernatant was previously evaporated, while dry residue was then dissolved in water/methanol solution in order to measure the PTX concentration by UV/VIS spectrophotometry. The formulae used to calculate PTX concentration are: $A = 0.0291c + 0.0303$ (pH 5/methanol(65.8%)), $A = 0.0322c + 0.0472$ (pH 6/methanol(65.8%)), $A = 0.0314c + 0.0466$ (pH 7.4/methanol(65.8%)) and $A = 0.0291c + 0.0303$ (water/methanol(65.8%)), where A is the absorbance of the sample at 230 nm.

Measurements of release kinetics of GdB and PTX

GdB release measurements were performed from suspensions at different pH (in acetate buffer at pH 5.0, and in PBS at pH 6.0 and 7.4) of the prepared materials at a concentration of 0.5 mg/mL. At predetermined time points, the suspensions were centrifuged, and the supernatants were analyzed to determine the amount of GdB released by measuring the fluorescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 274$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 312$ nm). After the measurements, the solid residues of the materials were re-dispersed in the supernatants and returned to stirring until the next time point. All measurements were performed in triplicate.

The release of PTX was performed from a suspension of materials (PTX@BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN) in solvent mixtures containing 65.8% methanol and 34.2% of acetate buffer at pH 5 or PBS at pH 7.4. At predetermined time points, the suspensions were centrifuged, and the supernatants were analyzed by UV/VIS measurements to determine the amount of released PTX based on the absorbance peak at 230 nm.

Scanning electron microscopy

SEM images were obtained using a Tescan MIRA3 XMU FESEM. The samples were previously coated with a thin layer of Au using a standard sputtering technique. Three images for each material were analyzed by ImageJ software to determine the range of particle diameters.

Transmission electron microscopy

TEM characterization was conducted in a FEI Talos F200X microscope, operated at 200 keV voltage, in conventional mode. The samples were prepared following a standard procedure where the nanoparticles were first dispersed into ethanol and then a drop of the solution was placed on a carbon-coated Cu grid, which was allowed to dry in air.

Nitrogen adsorption-desorption measurements

The analyses were conducted using an Anton Paar NOVAtouch LX2 instrument after degassing materials for 6 hours at 105 °C in vacuum. Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) specific surface area of materials was calculated from the adsorption branch, in the relative pressure range from 0.05 to 0.3 P/P°. Barrett,

Joyner and Halenda (BJH) calculations of pore diameter were performed on the desorption branch of the isotherm.

Thermogravimetric analyses

The TGA and DSC analyses were performed using a DTA-TG-DSC - Netzsch STA 449 F5 Jupiter (Figure S3). Typically, 5 mg of materials were measured, and the analyses were performed in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Spectrophotometric measurements

UV/VIS absorbance and fluorescence spectra were recorded on a UV-Vis spectrometer - Jasco V-750 and Spectrofluorometer - Jasco FP-8550, respectively. The measurements conditions are provided above. FTIR spectra have been obtained by the transmission KBr pellet technique using a Thermo-Nicolet Nexus 670 instrument.

Dynamic light scattering and zeta potential measurements

DLS and zeta potential of the synthesized nanoparticles were recorded on a Particle size analyzer—Litesizer 500 (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria). The hydrodynamic diameter of the starting MPMSN and BMPH-MPMSN materials was obtained by conducting the measurements on suspensions of the materials in water at a final concentration of 0.1 mg/mL in quintuplicate. The DLS investigation of the stability of CHX-CD-BMPH-MPMSN and CD-BMPH-MSN materials in cell medium, and PTX@BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN in PBS, were performed in triplicate at a final concentration of 0.1 mg/mL and 0.05 mg/mL, immediately after 30 minutes of sonication and after 1 h of incubation at room temperature without agitation.

Testing materials on glioblastoma cells

U87 cells (acquired from the American Type Culture Collection) were used to assess the developed nanosystems *in vitro*. The cells were cultured at 37°C in an atmosphere of 5% carbon dioxide and 95% air, in MEM containing 1% L-glutamine, phenol red and 10% fetal bovine serum. Cells were split twice a week.

Cellular uptake experiments

All FITC-labelled materials (FITC-BMPH-MPMSN, CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN) were incubated with U87 cells to study NPs internalization by both confocal microscopy and flow cytometry. To analyze NPs internalization by confocal microscopy, U87 cells were seeded at a concentration of 35,000 cells/well in duplicates in IBIDI μ -slide 8 well chamber slides, incubated overnight and treated with the different sets of NPs at a concentration of 50 μ g/mL during 2, 4 and 6 h. Then, the cells were washed twice with PBS, fixed with 4% formaldehyde for 20 min, washed again with PBS and stained. Hoechst 33258 (1 μ g/mL) was used to stain the nuclei, while ActinRed™ 555 ReadyProbes™ Reagent by Invitrogen (2 drops/mL) were used to stain cell membranes. After further washes with PBS,

the cells were observed with a Leica SP8 laser confocal microscope (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany).

For flow cytometry experiments, U87 cells were seeded at a concentration of 300,000 cells/well in 6-well plates (by duplicate), incubated overnight and treated with 50 µg/mL NPs during 2, 4 and 6 h. Then, the cells were washed with media and PBS, detached with trypsin, centrifuged, and fixed with 4% formaldehyde for 20 min. After centrifugation, the cells were resuspended in PBS and the cell-associated fluorescence (CAF= % positive cells * mean fluorescence intensity) was measured by flow cytometry using a BD Accuri™ C6 Flow Cytometer (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA).

Cell viability assays

The effects of different sets of nanomaterials on cell viability were also studied in U87 cells. For this purpose, 4,000 cells/well were seeded in 96-well plates in triplicates, incubated overnight and then treated with a range of NPs concentrations (from 1.56 to 100 µg/mL) and further incubated during 24, 48 and 72 h. Cell viability was then measured using the Cell Proliferation/Cytotoxicity Assay CCK-8 by Dojindo, following the supplier's instructions. The absorbance in the plates was measured at 450 nm using a BioTek Synergy H1 microplate reader (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA).

Measurement of longitudinal relaxation time (T_1)

Suspensions of the materials (10 mg/mL) were prepared in PBS buffer pH 7.4 (10 mM) and acetate buffer pH 5 (10 mM). As soon as suspensions were made, solutions were transferred to 1 mL syringes and placed in a sample holder for scanning. MRI was done using a 7-Tesla preclinical scanner (Bruker, Ettlingen, Germany) with an actively shielded gradient (BGA20SHP) system, maximum 300 mT/m gradient strength, and 40 mm quadrature birdcage coil. Longitudinal relaxation time (T_1) was measured using a saturation recovery method with a variable repetition time and rapid acquisition with relaxation enhancement (RAREVTR); TR = 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0 s, echo time (TE) = 6.68 ms, RARE factor = 2, 117 µm² in-plane resolution, 1 mm slice thickness, NEX = 1. Image processing and T_1 quantification was done offline using ImageJ (National Institutes of Health; imagej.nih.gov/ij/), and the MRI analysis calculator plugin written by Karl Schmidt.

To convert measured T_1 values of BMPH-MPMSN suspensions to released GdB in mg/mL, a series of GdB solutions (0.1, 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 mg/mL) were prepared at two different pH values (5.0 and 7.4) and the linear curve was fitted using equation: $R_1 = R_1^0 + r_1[\text{GdB}]$, where $R_1 = 1/T_1$ is measured relaxation rate of the GdB solution, R_1^0 is the relaxation rate of buffer solution without GdB, $[\text{GdB}]$ is the concentration of GdB and r_1 is the longitudinal relaxivity of GdB calculated as a slope of the linear fit.

Statistical analysis

For cell experiments three independent experiments were carried out in duplicate or triplicate as stated. Data was analysed using GraphPad Prism 8 software (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA). All means

are reported with standard deviation. Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Sidak's multiple comparisons test were performed as appropriate. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The MSN material was synthesized by following the well-established methodology that involves surfactant-templated and base-catalyzed co-condensation of silica precursors (TEOS and MPTMS).³⁴ Further functionalization with N-beta-maleimidopropionic acid hydrazide (BMPH) was used as a crosslinker between mercaptopropyl-functionalized MSNs and the pore blocking agent – β -CD-CHO, which yields in entrapment of the cargo molecules in the process (Scheme 1a,b). Further functionalization with CHX was achieved by its covalent attachment to adamantane-amine and strong host-guest interactions between adamantane and the pore-capping β -cyclodextrin moieties (Scheme 1c). Figure 1 shows the SEM and TEM images of the MPMSN and BMPH-MPMSN materials. The SEM images evidence spherical morphology of the particles with a diameter in the range of 100–250 nm, while TEM images confirm the structured particle porosity.

The low angle XRD measurements (Fig. 2a) revealed that the MSN material exhibits 2D-hexagonal pore structure, which is not significantly influenced after functionalization with BMPH. The presence of the BMPH functional group on the MSNs is evident from the Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectrum of the BMPH-MPMSN material (Fig. 2b), with the band at 1701 cm^{-1} ascribed to the vibrations of the carbonyl groups of BMPH. The TGA and DSC curves confirm the successful functionalization of BMPH (Figure S3). Even though the TGA curves show overlapping weight loss patterns, careful analysis confirms that in the case of BMPH-MPMSN material there is an additional 1% weight loss, in the range between 250–700 °C, in comparison to the starting MPMSN, which can be ascribed to the functionalized BMPH group. The DSC curves clearly show a pronounced exothermic band centered around 560 °C, which further evidences the presence of BMPH. The hydrodynamic diameter of the particles and their zeta potential, as measured in aqueous suspension at 0.1 mg/mL do not change significantly after functionalization (Table 1).

Table 1
Particle size and zeta potential of prepared materials

Material	Weight loss (% \pm SD) between 300 and 700°C	Hydrodynamic Diameter (nm \pm SD)	Zeta potential (mV \pm SD)
MPMSN	22.35 \pm 0.13	250.9 \pm 11.4	-23.5 \pm 1.2
BMPH-MPMSN	23.38 \pm 0.14	250.5 \pm 7.4	-25.6 \pm 0.6

Nitrogen sorption measurements confirmed the functionalization of MPMSN with BMPH, as the surface area, calculated using the Brunauer, Emmett and Teller (BET) method, is reduced from 864 m²/g to 773 m²/g and the pore volume from 0.53 cm³ to 0.47 cm³ after functionalization. Both materials show the same predominant pore size peak at 1.9 nm and the average pore size at 2.4 nm (Table 2), determined

following the Barrett, Joyner and Halenda (BJH) method. The isotherms of both materials are clearly type IV before loading (Fig. 3a), without evident hystereses. However, after the loading of GdB and PTX and capping with CD-CHO, the BET isotherm changes to types I and II (Fig. 3b), which is typically observed in the case of MSNs with the capped mesopores. Notably, BET specific surface areas and pore volumes also decrease, as noted in Table 2. Higher loading capacity was noted in the case of materials loaded with GdB in comparison with PTX, possibly related to the lower molecular weight of GdB.

Table 2
BET and BJH characteristics of the starting materials

Material	Surface Area (m ² /g ± SD)	BJH predominant peak (nm ± SD)	Average Pore Size (nm ± SD)	Total Pore Volume (cm ³ /g ± SD)
MPMSN	864 ± 17	1.93 ± 0.04	2.44 ± 0.05	0.53 ± 0,01
BMPH- MPMSN	773 ± 15	1.90 ± 0.04	2.43 ± 0.05	0.47 ± 0,01

Table 3 gives information about the amounts of encapsulated GdB and PTX. These were determined from the filtrates and the standard curves obtained with fluorescence spectroscopy for GdB and UV/VIS spectroscopy for PTX (Figures S1 and S2), as detailed in the experimental section. The release of GdB was further monitored with fluorescence measurements in aqueous environment at different pH values. The measurements were performed on supernatants, after removal of the materials by centrifugation at designated time points, with excitation at 280 nm and monitoring the emission at 312 nm. The results revealed similar kinetics for the materials with and without functionalized CHX (Fig. 4a), as would be expected since the same pH-sensitive linkage and the same cargo molecules are used for the two materials. Evidently, the release of GdB is enhanced in weakly acidic environment, especially at pH 5 in comparison to the higher pH values. It is noticeable, particularly at pH 5, that the amount of released GdB in supernatants decreases after the first measurement. It is possible that this effect is due to re-adsorption of GdB onto the surface of the materials after the initial release. The maximum release was noted after 30 minutes of stirring and determined to be 63.5 ± 2.9 mg of GdB/g of CHX-GdB@BMPH-MPMSN (38.7 ± 1.7% of the loaded GdB), while in the case of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN the maximum release is 56.6 ± 7.4 milligrams of GdB per gram of the material (29.7 ± 3.9% of the loaded amount), as determined from the standard curve. In the case of 1 mg/mL suspension of the materials, after 30 minutes CHX-GdB@BMPH-MPMSN released GdB in a concentration of 102.0 ± 1.5 μM while in the case of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN, the concentration of GdB released is 91.0 ± 2.9 μM.

The release kinetics of PTX from the PTX@BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN materials was measured by UV/VIS measurements in the buffer (acetate pH 5 or PBS pH 7.4)/methanol mixtures (Fig. 4b). Evidently, in case of both materials, significantly higher amount of PTX was released at pH 5 vs. pH 7.4, which agrees with the obtained results for GdB loaded materials. However, no re-adsorption of

PTX on the MSN surface was noticed, as it happened in the case of GdB release, possibly due to weaker interaction of PTX with the MSN surface.

Table 3

BET surface area, total pore volume, and loading capacity of the prepared cargo-loaded materials.

Material	BET surface area (m ² /g ± SD)	Total Pore Volume (cm ³ /g ± SD)	Amount of loaded drug (mg drug or CA/ g material ± SD)
CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN	22 ± 1	0.17 ± 0.003	79.2 ± 0.2
CD-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN	234 ± 5	0.32 ± 0,006	17.2 ± 0,1
CHX-GdB@BMPH-MPMSN	196 ± 4	0.19 ± 0.004	163.9 ± 2.5
GdB@BMPH-MPMSN	224 ± 4	0.20 ± 0.004	190.4 ± 2.9

To evaluate their potential for biological applications, we first investigated the internalization capabilities of the prepared materials in U87 cells, using confocal microscopy and flow cytometry. The confocal microscopy results at different time points are shown in Fig. 5. We tested three different materials labeled with FITC without any cargo molecules: the first one with no capping, the second one capped with β -cyclodextrin and the third one capped with β -cyclodextrin and functionalized with CHX. All the materials showed the ability to enter U87 cells after 4 or 6 h. The results are in agreement with our expectations, as MSNs internalization normally occurs a few hours after their administration, although there may be variations depending on the NPs' functionalization or the employed cell line.³⁵⁻³⁷

The flow cytometry results (Figure S4 and Fig. 6) revealed that CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN are the best internalized NPs by U87 cell, while the uptake of CHX-CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN is lower than the other two. This result could be explained by the possible aggregation in the cell medium of the NPs after functionalization with CHX, which then hinders their endocytosis. The results of DLS measurements performed on the suspension of the capped materials without loaded cargo molecules in cell medium confirmed this assumption (Figure S5 and Figure S6). The measurements revealed a hydrodynamic diameter of 584 ± 77 nm for CD-BMPH-MPMSN and 739 ± 58 nm for CHX-CD-BMPH-MPMSN immediately after preparing the dispersion and intensive sonication, that increased to 808 ± 81 nm and 980 ± 181 nm, respectively, after 1h incubation. Therefore, both types of particles show a tendency to aggregate in cell medium, with the enhanced aggregation for the material functionalized with CHX. The aggregation of particles in PBS is less pronounced, evidenced by the hydrodynamic diameter of PTX@CD-BMPH-MPMSN measured as 311 ± 55 nm before and 334 ± 83 nm after 1h incubation in PBS, while for PTX@CHX-CD-BMPH, the obtained values were 374 ± 15 nm before and 503 ± 42 nm after one hour incubation (Figure S7). However, even in PBS the CHX-functionalized material shows enhanced

susceptibility to aggregation vs. the material without CHX, as clearly evidenced by the shift of the peaks to higher diameters for all three DLS measurements after 1 h of incubation.

The effect of the prepared materials on cell viability was further evaluated in U87 cells. As shown in Fig. 7, the exposure to the GdB loaded materials during 24, 48 or 72 h showed similar cytotoxic effects, with and without CHX grafting. Namely, both materials showed the ability to kill U87 cancer cells at concentrations above 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. At such concentration, the corresponding concentration of loaded GdB in GdB@BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-GdB@BMPH-MPMSN is 4.75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 4.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively.

The cytotoxic effects of the materials loaded with PTX were further evaluated on the same cell line. As can be observed in Fig. 8, FITC-labeled starting material (FITC-BMPH-MPMSN) did not show significant toxicity except at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, after 48 or 72 h of exposure. The corresponding FITC-labeled materials capped with CD or CD and CHX, instead, do not appear to affect cell viability even at the highest concentrations and longer exposure times tested (Figure S8). However, upon co-incubating the cells with materials loaded with PTX, a significant enhancement of the toxicity was noted even after 24h of treatment. As the experiments were performed in media at physiological pH, we speculate that the acidic environment of the endosomes could trigger the release of the cargo loaded from the NPs. A notable difference was found also between the two materials loaded with PTX. Evidently, the NPs with CHX on the surface induced a higher cytotoxic effect on U87 cells, despite the previously observed lower cellular uptake, which could be ascribed to a higher loaded amount of PTX in the CHX-capped material.

Finally, we evaluated the MRI capabilities of the material with the highest amount of loaded GdB (GdB@BMPH-MPMSN) in weakly acidic vs. physiological pH condition. Toward that end, all MRI measurements were performed at different time points using the GdB@BMPH-MPMSN material suspended (10 mg/mL) in buffers at pH 5.0 and 7.4 and compared to the suspension of MPMSN material as a negative control. As shown in pseudo-colored images of the samples (Fig. 9a), the differences are particularly evident in the case of comparing the GdB loaded materials vs. MPMSN. By qualitative estimation, only minor differences can be detected through comparison of the pseudo-colored images of the suspensions of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN at different pH. Though, a clear difference can be noted in the case of taking the MRIs of only supernatants after 48 h of incubation. Evidently, in the applied conditions the materials tend to precipitate from suspension and concentrate on the bottom of the measuring cuvettes. Hence, to quantitatively characterize the obtained MR images, we applied the methodology of measuring longitudinal relaxation times (T_1) in the bottom as well as at the top of the cuvettes, with the same region of interest (ROI) for all samples (Figure S9). The calculated values of T_1 in the areas of bulk solution and the precipitate are shown in Figure S10, which reveals that in the case of the suspensions of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN, the same T_1 was obtained in the areas of the precipitate at the two pH, though in case of the bulk solution, the shorter T_1 was obtained in the case of the material at pH 5, vs, the material at pH 7.4 ($p < 0.05$ at all measured time points). These differences in T_1 in the bulk solution above the precipitated materials can be correlated with the enhanced release of GdB from the mesopores in weakly acidic conditions. Furthermore, the MRI measurements of the supernatants after 48 of incubation (Figure S11) revealed that the supernatant of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN at pH 5 showed the

lowest T1 (2.3 s), followed by the supernatant of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN at 7.4 (2.6 s), which were significantly lower than the T1 of supernatants from the MPMSN materials (2.9 s). Finally, we determined the concentration of the released GdB in bulk solution from the obtained T1 values based on the prepared standard curves of GdB at pH 5.0 and 7.4 (Fig. 9a, b). Evidently, the highest concentration of GdB was observed at the 1.5 h point in the case of the GdB@BMPH-MPMSN material at pH 5 (0.031 ± 0.03 mg/mL), while at pH 7.4, the same material released half of that GdB concentration (0.016 ± 0.006 mg/mL).

DISCUSSION

The released amounts of GdB in the MRI experiments are much lower than the values expected from the release kinetics measurements (Fig. 4). This difference could be attributed to the fact that for the release kinetics studies, the suspensions of the materials at concentrations of 0.05 mg/mL were stirred vigorously, which produced the optimal conditions for the diffusion from the pores and maximum release of GdB (0.028 ± 0.009 mg/mL and 0.009 ± 0.005 mg/mL, at pH 5 and pH 7.4 respectively). On the other hand, the MRI experiments were performed at a 20-fold higher concentration (10 mg/mL) in conditions where the suspension was not stirred, leading to low GdB diffusion efficiency from the mesopores and enhanced re-adsorption rate on the MSN surface. This is probably one of the reasons for the obtained low intensity of MR images of suspensions with the CA-loaded materials.

Nevertheless, the experiment clearly proves the concept that MRI tracking of the release contrast agents from the nanotheranostic devices is possible. Although important adjustments are needed for further application of this MRI methodology in a real-life setting, as significantly higher relaxivities by the contrast agents are required for *in vivo* applications. This could be achieved in the future by devising nanotheranostics with higher release capacity of CAs, by improving and optimizing the structure and functionalization of nanomaterials as well as by optimizing the protocols and sensitivity of MRI measurements.

In a recent study, the release of the MRI contrast agent gadopentetate dimeglumine from MSN mesopores was demonstrated upon exposure to high-intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU), which was also monitored by MRI.³⁸ The results revealed that the signal intensity on T1-weighted MR images of the material as measured in agarose gel decreased upon the release of the CA from the mesopores. This effect was rationalized by the fact that with the CAs within the mesopores, signal intensity is high due to low rotational tumbling time of the CAs.³⁹ However, the effect was observed for the MSN that contained positively charged functional groups inside the mesopores while the CA was negatively charged, and hence the decrease in the tumbling rate of CAs occurred due to an electrostatic binding of CAs to the functional groups inside the mesopores. On the contrary, the pore surface in our study is functionalized with noncharged mercapto groups, which could not decrease the tumbling rate of the negatively charged GdB through electrostatic binding. In fact, as sulfur is known as a strong donor atom, it is possible that mercapto groups within the pores serve as ligands which bind to the central Gd(III) of GdB to some extent. In that case the signal intensity on T1-weighted MR image decreases, as water molecules require

access to the CA coordination sphere for the ligand exchange process and contrast enhancement. This is a probable reason behind the lower signal intensity observed for the CA-loaded MSNs in our study, considering that the loading capacity of the CA in our study is only slightly lower (19%) in comparison to the published study (24%),³⁸ and therefore no substantial differences in signal intensity were expected. Hence, further consideration is needed regarding the applied surface functionalization but also in relation to the applied field strength and the diameter of the pores, as a recent publication revealed that using a 1.5 T field strength and CAs confined in the pores of 30–40 nm favor enhanced CA relaxivity.⁴⁰

Ideally, if the materials and the MRI measurements are optimized sufficiently for *in vivo* applications, the release of CAs upon exposure to stimuli, such as acidification, may allow a real-time insight into the location and the efficiency of release from the NPs at the target tissue. This would be of particular importance for monitoring the capability of DDSs to deliver drugs to the desired site, such as tumor tissues, and for excluding the NPs that deliver their cargo to healthy tissues. Furthermore, the tracking of the changes in signal intensity upon the pH-responsive release of CAs could be applicable for MRI-based *in vivo* sensing of tissue pH, while novel CA-loaded nanoparticles may be developed for *in vivo* sensing and tracking of different biomolecules. which could be capable of triggering the release the CAs.⁴¹

Abbreviations

MRI-Magnetic resonance imaging

MSN-Mesoporous silica nanoparticles

MPMSN-mercaptopropyl-MSN

CHX-Chlorotoxin

GdB-Gadobutrol

PTX-Paclitaxel

CD- β -cyclodextrin

CD-CHO- β -cyclodextrin monoaldehyde

GBM-Glioblastoma Multiforme

CA-contrast agent

SEM-Scanning electron microscopy

TEM-Transmission electron microscopy

XRD-X-ray diffraction

BET- Brunauer–Emmett–Teller

BJH-Barrett-Joyner-Halenda

DLS-Dynamic light scattering

TGA-thermogravimetric analysis

DSC-differential scanning calorimetry

FTIR- Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

BMPH-N- β -maleimidopropionic acid hydrazide

FITC-Fluorescein isothiocyanate

NIR- near infra-red

CONCLUSION

The contrast agent GdB and the anticancer drugs PTX were successfully entrapped inside pH-responsive mesoporous silica-based nanomaterials. The GdB- and PTX-loaded MSNs were capped with β -cyclodextrin, covalently attached to the functionalized MSN, and further functionalized with CHX for the purpose of targeting Glioblastoma Multiforme. The released amounts of the contrast agent GdB and anticancer drug PTX were enhanced in weakly acidic conditions in comparison to the release at the physiological pH. Confocal microscopy and flow cytometry measurements revealed that all tested materials are endocytosed by the U87 cells. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that GdB- and PTX-loaded materials exhibit a cytotoxic effect on these cells, with the highest toxicity observed for the CHX-functionalized PTX-loaded material. Finally, the MRI measurements on buffered suspensions of the materials confirmed the capabilities of this methodology to identify enhanced release of CAs at weakly acidic conditions. The obtained proof-of-concept results are promising toward future applications of this MRI-based methodology for possible testing of different CA-loaded nanotheranostics, which might enable identification of optimized drug delivery systems in terms of their targeted drug delivery capabilities to specific tissues and diminished adverse effects, *en route* to a more personalized treatment of cancer. It is envisioned that the use of contrast agent-loaded NPs could be applied in the future, prior to the treatment with the drug-filled analogues. This would allow rapid assessment of the ability of nanotherapeutics to release their therapeutic loading and reveal the biodistribution of the released cargo, which could effectively lead to a more personalized clinical management of cancer patients.

Abbreviations

MRI

Magnetic resonance imaging

MSN
Mesoporous silica nanoparticles
MPMSN
mercaptopropyl-MSN
CHX
Chlorotoxin
GdB
Gadobutrol
PTX
Paclitaxel
CD
 β -cyclodextrin
CD
CHO- β -cyclodextrin monoaldehyde
GBM
Glioblastoma Multiforme
CA
contrast agent
SEM
Scanning electron microscopy
TEM
Transmission electron microscopy
XRD
X-ray diffraction
BET
Brunauer-Emmett-Teller
BJH
Barrett-Joyner-Halenda
DLS
Dynamic light scattering
TGA
thermogravimetric analysis
DSC
differential scanning calorimetry
FTIR
Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
BMPH
N- β -maleimidopropionic acid hydrazide
FITC
Fluorescein isothiocyanate

NIR
near infra-red

Declarations

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting information is available: TGA and DSC of MPMSN and BMPH-MPMSN; calibration curves for GdB and PTX at different pH; representative histograms and dot plots showing FITC-BMPH-MP-MSNs, CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN internalization in U87 cells at different time points; DLS size measurements in cell medium at 0.1 mg/mL concentration immediately after dispersing CD-BMPH-MPMSN and CDX-CD-BMPH-MPMSN, as well as after 1h incubation; DLS size measurements in PBS at 0.05 mg/mL concentration immediately after dispersing and after 1h of incubation of PTX@BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN; U87 cells viability after 72 h of incubation with different concentrations of CD-FITC-BMPH-MP-MSNs or CHX-CD-FITC-BMPH-MP-MSNs; measured MRI images of the GdB@BMPH-MPMSN and MPMSN materials; Values of longitudinal relaxation times (T1) of suspensions of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN and MPMSN at pH 7.4 and pH 5; measured MRI images of the supernatants after centrifugation of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN and MPMSN materials after 48 h of incubation

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scheme 1

scheme 1 is available in the Supplementary Files section.

Figures

Figure 1

SEM (a, b) and TEM (c, d) micrographs of MPMSN (a, c) and BMPH-MPMSN (b, d).

Figure 2

a) Low angle XRD and b) FTIR of MPMSN and BMPH-MPMSN

Figure 3

a) BET isotherms and BJH pore distribution (inset) of MPMSN and BMPH-MPMSN and b) BET isotherms of BMPH-MPMSN materials loaded with GdB and PTX.

Figure 4

a) Release of GdB from GdB@BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-GdB@BMPH-MPMSN at pH 5.0, 6.0, and 7.4. Inset shows the first two hours of GdB release; b) Release of PTX from PTX@BMPH-MPMSN and CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN at pH 5.0 and 7.4.

Figure 5

Representative confocal microscopy images of U87 cells after 2, 4 or 6 h of incubation with 50 μg/mL of FITC-BMPH-MPMSNs, CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSNs or CHX-CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSNs. Cell nuclei are stained with Hoechst 33258 (blue) and cellular membrane with ActinRed™ 555 ReadyProbes™ Reagent (red). NPs are labeled with FITC (green). Scale bar= 100 μm.

Figure 6

Cell-associated fluorescence over time of U87 cells treated with 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of FITC-BMPH-MPMSN, CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN or CHX-CD-FITC-BMPH-MPMSN, expressed as mean \pm SD (n= 2).

Figure 7

U87 cells viability after 24, 48 or 72 h of incubation with different concentrations of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN or CHX-GdB@BMPH-MPMSN. Cell viability was analyzed by measuring absorbance at 450 nm with the CCK-8 reagent. Three independent experiments containing triplicates were performed. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Two-way ANOVA and Sidak's multiple comparisons test were applied (* $p < 0.05$ vs control, # $p < 0.05$).

Figure 8

U87 cells viability after 24, 48 or 72 h of incubation with different concentrations of FITC-BMPH-MPMSN, PTX@BMPH-MPMSN or CHX-PTX@BMPH-MPMSN. Cell viability was analyzed by measuring absorbance at 450 nm with the CCK-8 reagent. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Two-way ANOVA and Sidak's multiple comparisons test were applied (* $p < 0.05$ vs control, # $p < 0.05$).

Figure 9

a) T_1 -maps (pseudo-colored) of GdB@BMPH-MPMSN and MPMSN suspensions at pH 7.4 and pH 5, and supernatants after 48 h of incubation; **b)** Gadobutrol concentrations [mg/mL] \pm SD in GdB@BMPH-MPMSN in the bulk solution calculated based on **(c)** linear fitting of GdB known concentrations vs. longitudinal relaxation rate ($R_1=1/T_1$) for pH 5.0 and pH 7.4.

Supplementary Files

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- [Scheme1.tiff](#)
- [KnezevicetalSupplementalInformationJNBT.docx](#)
- [TOCfigure.tiff](#)